

**Exploring Recombination Rates in Fleckvieh and Braunvieh Cattle Breeds and their
Correlation with SNP and GC Content Densities**

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	Single Cell Genomics lab at Johannes Kepler University
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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Exploring Recombination Rates in Fleckvieh and Braunvieh Cattle Breeds and their Correlation with SNP and GC Content Densities project, delivered in M4. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the Horizon Europe DMP template.

Fardokht Sadat Mohammadi will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

The reference genome of Bos Taurus obtained from NCBI is reused for calculating the GC content of specific regions of chromosome 25. Reusing the reference genome ensures consistency and accuracy in the GC content calculations and eliminates the need for redundant sequencing and assembly efforts.

The genotyped data previously generated for Braunvieh and Fleckvieh breeds by the Single Cell Genomics lab at JKU are reused to estimate recombination rates, SNP densities, and GC content for specific regions of chromosome 25. Reusing this data allows for efficient utilization of existing resources and ensures consistency in the genetic background of the studied populations.

Furthermore, repurposing existing data reduces the need for additional data generation, which can be costly and time-consuming.

The project generates and re-uses the following types and formats of data:

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Braunvieh and Fleckvieh recombination rates	Other	RDS (R Data Serialization)	1 GB	no
P2	GC Content of a genomic subset along chromosome 25 in Bos Taurus Reference Genome	Plain text	TXT	100 MB	no
P3	SNP densities for a subset of chromosome 25 for both	Plain text	TXT	100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
	Braunvieh and Fleckvieh				

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Braunvieh genotype data	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085772	Restricted data. Access can be granted upon request.	no
R2	Fleckvieh genotype data	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085772	Restricted data. Access can be granted upon request.	no
R3	Genome assembly ARS-UCD1.2	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/genome/GCF_002263795.1/	Public data	no

The purpose of data generation or re-use in this project is closely aligned with the objectives of the study conducted by the Single Cell Genomics lab. The main project focus of the lab revolves around investigating recombination rates and factors influencing recombination events. Additionally, the lab conducts research on specific populations of cows, resulting in extensive available data.

Therefore, the decision was made to investigate recombination rates and factors influencing recombination in two distinct breeds of cows. By leveraging the extensive data available for these populations, the project aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. **Characterization of Recombination Rates:** Generate fine-scale, breed-specific maps of recombination rates for a subset of chromosome 25 in Braunvieh and Fleckvieh cattle breeds.
2. **Identification of Correlates:** Investigate associations between recombination rates and genomic features such as SNP density and GC content.

3. Understanding Genetic Variation: Explore genetic variations and patterns within and between Braunvieh and Fleckvieh populations to gain insights into the genetic diversity and structure of these breeds.

By aligning with the objectives of the lab's main project, this study contributes to advancing understanding in the field of recombination genetics, particularly in the context of cattle populations. The investigation of recombination rates and associated factors in two distinct cattle breeds provides valuable insights into the mechanisms driving genetic diversity and evolution in livestock species.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The laboratory of Single Cell Genomics at the Johannes Kepler University has conducted genome sequencing for 81 Braunvieh and 161 Fleckvieh individuals in the past. Leveraging this existing genotype data, recombination rates were calculated using the [R-package LDJump](#) version 0.3.1. LDJump is a software tool designed to estimate recombination maps of population genetic data provided in VCF format. The process involved a two-step approach, including segmentation and regression modeling, to estimate recombination rates across specific genomic regions. Additionally, [custom R scripts](#) were developed to calculate the GC content for a subset of chromosome 25 using the reference genome of *Bos Taurus*. The calculated GC content enables the study of the relationship between recombination rates and GC content. Furthermore, SNP densities for the same subset of chromosome 25 were computed for both Braunvieh and Fleckvieh breeds using [custom R scripts](#). These scripts utilized the genotype information of each breed to quantify the density of single nucleotide polymorphisms along the chromosome, facilitating analysis of the relationship between recombination rates and SNP densities. Through these methods and software tools, the project aims to deepen understanding of genetic variation and recombination dynamics in Braunvieh and Fleckvieh cattle breeds.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

The data generated in this project could be useful to various stakeholders outside the immediate project scope. Potential beneficiaries include geneticists and researchers studying recombination and factors influencing it and they may utilize the dataset to investigate the mechanisms and drivers of recombination events in livestock species. Furthermore, breeders and farmers can benefit from insights into the genetic diversity and recombination patterns within Braunvieh and Fleckvieh cattle breeds. Understanding recombination rates and associated genomic features could inform breeding strategies aimed at improving desirable traits and enhancing overall herd health and productivity.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

We make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository provides means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

To structure the data and handle versioning effectively, reused and newly generated datasets along with the scripts used for data analysis and plotting are stored on GitHub. We create a dedicated repository on GitHub for datasets and scripts and organize datasets into directories, ensuring clear and intuitive navigation. We also use descriptive file and directory names to easily identify the contents of each dataset and script. Additionally, we include a README file in the repository to provide information about the datasets, scripts, and their intended use. For the versioning, we use the version control of Git to track changes to datasets and scripts over time. We establish some practices for writing informative commit messages detailing the modifications made. Additionally, we can use branching and tagging strategies to manage different versions of datasets and scripts, allowing for experimentation and development without affecting the main branch. Finally, we ensure that all contributors adhere to versioning guidelines and use branching appropriately when making changes or additions to the datasets and scripts through configuring GitHub settings. By structuring the data and scripts on GitHub and implementing version control with Git, we can maintain a well-organized and documented repository of datasets and scripts, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility for future analyses and collaborations.

To facilitate the discovery and reuse of the data and scripts stored on GitHub, the following metadata is provided:

Dataset Metadata:

- Title: Descriptive title indicating the content and purpose of the dataset.
- Description: Detailed description of the dataset, including its origin, content, and intended use.
- Creator: Name or research group responsible for generating and managing the dataset.
- Affiliation: Affiliation or institution associated with the creator of the dataset.
- Contact Information: Contact details, such as email address, for inquiries or assistance regarding the dataset.
- Keywords: Relevant keywords or tags to aid in searchability and categorization of the dataset.
- License: Information about the licensing terms under which the dataset is released.
- Access Restrictions: Details regarding any access restrictions or permissions required to access the dataset.
- Data Format: Description of the format in which the dataset is stored (e.g., CSV, VCF, RDS).
- Data Size: Approximate size of the dataset in terms of file size or number of records.
- Data Source: Information about the source or origin of the dataset, including any relevant publications or projects.
- Additional Information: Any additional details or metadata relevant to understanding and using the dataset effectively.

Script Metadata:

- Title: Descriptive title indicating the purpose or function of the script.
- Description: Detailed description of the script, including its functionality, input requirements, and output.
- Creator: Name or research group responsible for developing and maintaining the script.
- Affiliation: Affiliation or institution associated with the creator of the script.

- **Contact Information:** Contact details, such as email address, for inquiries or assistance regarding the script.
- **Keywords:** Relevant keywords or tags to aid in searchability and categorization of the script.
- **License:** Information about the licensing terms under which the script is released.
- **Access Restrictions:** Details regarding any access restrictions or permissions required to access or use the script.
- **Language:** Programming language in which the script is written (e.g., Python, R, Bash).
- **Dependencies:** List of dependencies or requirements needed to run the script, including software libraries or packages.
- **Additional Information:** Any additional details or metadata relevant to understanding and using the script effectively.

By providing comprehensive metadata for both the datasets and scripts, we ensure that other researchers can easily discover, understand, and reuse the data and scripts for their own purposes. This helps others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

As far as possible, we use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Additionally, the data is be identified by a persistent identifier in the form of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) assigned to the GitHub repository. This DOI serves as a permanent link to the repository, ensuring that the data remains discoverable and citable over time. Users can reference the DOI in publications, citations, and other scholarly works to provide a reliable link to the scripts and datasets.

2.2. Making data accessible

We make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-04-29	GitHub	https://zenodo.org/records/11091912	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open		2024-04-29	GitHub	https://zenodo.org/records/11091912	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open		2024-04-29	GitHub	https://zenodo.org/records/11091912	CC-BY-4.0

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the

collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world.

Methods or software needed to access and use data:

Users need to utilize R programming language to load and access the estimated recombination rates stored in RDS (R Data Serialization) format. Users require a text editor to open and view the SNP density and GC content files.

2.3. Making data interoperable

We make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We utilize widely recognized data and metadata standards relevant to our field, such as those established by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), and the Research Data Alliance (RDA). Whenever possible, we try to store the data in open, non-proprietary file formats that are widely supported and easily accessible, such as TXT, FASTA, and VCF for genomics data. Furthermore, we provide good documentation for all our datasets.

Our data includes qualified references to other data, including datasets from our project as well as datasets from previous research. These references are carefully documented and cited providing context and linking related data resources. By referencing other datasets, we aim to promote interoperability, facilitate data integration, and acknowledge the contributions of previous research to our own work. Additionally, these references enable users to explore related data and build upon existing knowledge, fostering collaboration and advancing scientific inquiry.

2.4. Increase data re-use

We make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data are always assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained are published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

To provide the necessary documentation for validating data analysis and data use, the following measures are taken. A detailed explanation of the datasets generated, and the plots created is included in the bachelor's thesis. The thesis serves as comprehensive documentation of the data analysis process, including methodologies, procedures, and interpretations of results. Specific sections of the thesis are dedicated to describing how the datasets were generated, the scripts and tools used for data analysis, and the rationale behind the data visualization techniques employed. The bachelor's thesis is made publicly accessible on GitHub. Clear instructions and access links are provided in the metadata of the datasets and scripts stored on GitHub, directing users to the thesis for detailed documentation. Comments and annotations are also added within the scripts themselves to provide additional context and explanation for the data analysis steps performed.

The quality checks are done by peer review of scripts and data.

3. Other research outputs

For digital outputs such as software we utilize version control systems such as Git to manage software code and track changes over time and host code repositories on platforms GitHub to facilitate collaboration and version tracking. We document software and workflows using standardized formats such as README files and code comments. We apply open-source licenses to software code to encourage reuse and collaboration, while also protecting intellectual property rights. Furthermore, we ensure long-term preservation of software and workflows by archiving code repositories and associated documentation in institutional or domain-specific repositories.

4. Allocation of resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

The data manager directs the data management process overall, with the Single Cell Genomics lab at JKU being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers are responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data is ensured by the project manager. P2 (GC Content of a genomic subset along chromosome 25 in Bos Taurus Reference Genome), P3 (SNP densities for a subset of chromosome 25 for both Braunvieh and Fleckvieh), R1 (Braunvieh genotype data), R2 (Fleckvieh genotype data), P1 (Braunvieh and Fleckvieh recombination rates) are stored on GitHub. External storage is used because we host our scripts and datasets on github repositories, which not only provides version control capabilities with git but also serves as a centralized platform for collaboration and sharing.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	no access
R2	reading only	reading only	no access
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	GitHub	10 years
P2	GitHub	10 years
P3	GitHub	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

We will not make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.